

Borders Shaping
Perceptions of European Societies

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Executive summary

This report compiles the main results of the analysis of narratives in regional news media in four European border regions: the Danish-Swedish, Franco-German, Polish-German-Czech, and Slovak-Hungarian border regions. Utilising a narrative analytical framework, the case studies explore how media narratives shape perceptions of borders, European integration, and cross-border cooperation within the context of significant events like the Covid-19 pandemic or the migration crisis. The research defines narratives as structured stories encompassing temporal sequences, dramatic elements and symbols, aiming to convey plausible interpretations of events. Methodologically, the study employs qualitative analysis, combining bottom-up text analysis with top-down comparative enquiry across selected regional newspapers. The analysis covers the time period between the 2019 and 2024 European elections, a turbulent time in European integration that saw the Covid-19 pandemic, concerns over immigrants from outside the EU, as well as a number of local controversies.

This report seeks to answer the following research questions:

- How are the respective neighbours depicted in media narratives?
- How are processes of bordering and debordering presented in media narratives?
- How do these processes tie in with European integration and narratives about the EU?

In this, there is always a comparative dimension to highlight the similarities and differences between our case study border regions. Each of these regions is characterised by unique historical, political, and socio-cultural dynamics influencing narrative depictions of borders and neighbouring relations. At the same time, these regions share some commonalities, notably the fact that they are all internal EU borders, their coverage by the Schengen Agreement of open borders, and their recent experience of border closures. While borderlanders' voices tend to be sidelined in the regional media, a diverse set of actors are involved in constructing narratives in each of our case study regions, with journalists, as well as politicians at local, regional and European levels, taking a prominent position. Borderlanders' voices, in contrast, are more sidelined. The gender balance of the speakers is heavily skewed towards male voices in some of these categories and approaching near-parity in others. Care was taken in this report not to replicate these imbalances but rather to report narratives from a wide range of perspectives, including the perspectives of people of different genders.

In the characterisation of neighbours, one can detect a narrative of friendship, kinship and neighbourship in all case study regions. However, in the Polish-German-Czech border region as well as the Slovak-Hungarian border region, such narratives exist side by side with narratives of conflict and rivalry. Furthermore, in the Danish-Swedish, Polish-German-Czech and to a lesser extent Franco-German border region, there is a narrative of distant capitals not understanding local needs in the border region. The characterisation of the respective neighbours is sometimes linked to the European integration project, but only loosely.

Bordering measures such as border closures during the Covid-19 pandemic, in response to illicit migration or in response to crime are received differently in different media narratives. Border closures during the pandemic are often presented through the lens of auto(immunological) bordering. While some support for such bordering can be detected, the tenor of the media narratives in all case study regions is overwhelmingly opposed to border closures. This is because these closures affected key borderlands communities such as commuters, families or students. In contrast, there is far more support for bordering measures in response to migration from outside of the EU and in response to crime. In the regional media from the Danish-Swedish and Polish-German-Czech border regions in particular, bordering in response to crime and migration is presented through narratives of the securitisation of borders. In this narrative, border controls and closures are required to protect borderlands communities from these threats, and thus supported.

This differential support appears to connect with the question of whom the bordering measures target: when borderlanders such as commuters or families are affected, resistance to border closures is likely. In contrast, when migrants or criminals are the target, support for targeted closures is higher. There is also a link with the European level in this narrative of the securitisation of borders, insofar as narratives about the external EU border spill over into narratives of threat from migrants at some internal borders. Conversely, opposition to bordering measures during the Covid-19 pandemic is linked to the EU only in the Danish-Swedish and Slovak-Hungarian border regions, and only weakly.

Debordering is presented in the media narratives as functional integration or a return to a local transborder reality after Covid-19. Such narratives can be detected frequently. Furthermore, these narratives are reinforced by narratives opposing the Covid-19 border closures in all case study regions. Debordering narratives are linked with the EU in some instances, as they are often about Interreg projects resuming after the pandemic.

Narratives of a border region's relations with Europe and the European Union come in three flavours: Euroscepticism, Eurodistance, and Europhilia. Eurosceptic narratives of bureaucracy, a clash of European policies with local interests, and of EU encroachment on national values, can be detected in the Polish-German-Czech border region. In this region, local controversies such as that over the Turów coal mine dispute or the pollution in the river Odra, are also used as symbols in a narrative of a distant and impotent EU. In contrast, one can detect mainly Eurodistant narratives in the Danish-Swedish and Slovak-Hungarian border region. Eurodistant narratives present the EU as distant and inconsequential. This, in turn, goes hand in hand with a passive disengagement from the EU. Europhilia is strong in the Franco-German border region, but elements of this can also be detected in the Polish-German-Czech border region, where Eurosceptic and Europhilic narratives exist side by side, though the latter are stronger. Furthermore, there is a narrative of disappointment with the EU that stems from Europhilic hopes being dashed. Such disillusionment can sometimes promote more realistic assessments of the EU. At other times, it may stimulate efforts to emulate other border regions (often located in Western Europe) that are perceived as more successful in certain policy areas.

B-SHAPES' analytical framework has identified six narratives (crisis of/in Europe, (in)visibility of borders, (in)securitisation of borders, (auto)immunological crisis of borders, (in)humanitarian borders, and contesting borders in the name of Europe). This analysis shows that two of these are largely absent in the analysed media narratives. This is the case for narratives of (in)humanitarian borders and of contesting borders in the name of Europe. These two narratives did not feature, or featured only tangentially, in the regional media from our case study regions. In contrast, there is plenty of evidence of narratives of crisis in Europe, e.g. during the time of the Covid-19 pandemic, but also in terms of migration. Furthermore, migration as well as crime are linked to narratives of the securitisation of borders. Finally, the effects of the Covid-19 pandemic are often presented through narratives of (auto)immunological borders as well as the (in)visibility of borders.

The report concludes with insights into the complexities of border dynamics and European integration, emphasising the need for region-specific policies that address local realities while fostering broader European unity and cooperation. By unpacking narratives across diverse border regions, this study contributes to scholarly debates on European identity, cross-border relations, and the role of media in shaping public opinion and policy responses. The findings are crucial for policymakers, stakeholders, and researchers seeking to promote inclusive and effective strategies for European integration amidst evolving geopolitical landscapes and societal challenges.

Report

1. Theoretical Underpinnings

This report analyses narratives in regional and regionally-oriented news media in the Danish-Swedish, Franco-German, Polish-German-Czech and Slovak-Hungarian border regions. In B-SHAPES narratives are defined as stories ‘with a temporal sequence of events unfolding in a plot that is populated by dramatic moments, symbols, and archetypal characters that culminates in a moral to the story’ (Jones and McBeth, 2010, p. 329) and as ‘attempts by actors to develop and convey plausible accounts and interpretations of a phenomenon, event or series of events, person or a group of persons’ (Garcés-Mascareñas, 2021).

Narrative analysis has been applied productively to newspaper reporting (e.g. Harcourt et al., 2020; Pasquinelli and Trunfio, 2020). Media narratives shape policy and policy perception (Crow and Lawlor, 2016; Shanahan et al., 2011). In its focus on stories told with a purpose, B-SHAPES researchers analyse narratives not with a strict focus on a temporal sequence of events but rather as ‘kariotic time’, i.e. time structured by meaningful events (Czarniawska, 2010, p. 61).

Events that took place between the 2019 and 2024 European elections provided ample opportunities for narratives to be developed about borders, bordering and de-bordering processes and their connection with European integration. The Covid-19 pandemic affected the entire European space, but the pandemic was managed and perceived differently in different countries and regions. Because border regions are subject to at least two national policy regimes, single-jurisdictional decisions on border closures and checks affected both sides of a border region. There are also local events that tie in with broader historical, political and social contexts and that vary from border region to border region, and sometimes within one border region. Finally, in our analysis, we also make space to analyse the ‘absence’ of certain expected narratives, if only in some border regions.

We specifically looked for examples of the six border-related narratives identified by Opiłowska et al. (2023):

1. *The narrative of crisis of/in Europe*

This narrative links borders with crisis. Specifically, ‘crisis in Europe’ defines Europe as a canvas where the crisis occurs or is imported, but ‘crisis of Europe’ suggests that crisis is caused by Europe itself.

2. *The narrative of the (in)visibility of borders*

This narrative suggests that borders within the EU have become less visible for large parts of the population, whereas some individuals are much more likely to experience borders concretely.

3. *The narrative of the (in)securitisation of borders*

The securitisation narrative hinges on perceptions that borders are in crisis. In this narrative, strategies of re-bordering and the securitisation of borders are presented as remedies for insecurity and designed to assuage anxieties related to borders.

4. *The narrative of (auto)immunological crisis of borders*

Immunological borders are those that fulfil the function of protecting a body from pathogens. This narrative took on a concrete meaning during the Covid-19 pandemic, where narratives of 'Covid-bordering' in turn impinged on narratives of Europe.

5. *The narrative of (in)humanitarian borders*

This narrative points to a tension between ethical values and the narrative of borders in crisis. It highlights the way in which securitised borders may clash with humanitarian values, in turn generating calls for humanitarian action.

6. *The narrative of contesting borders (in the name of Europe)*

Following on from the narrative of (in)humanitarian borders, a self-critical narrative among Europeans has the effect of reinvigorating the universalist promise of the European idea. This idea encompasses Europe as the idea of a borderless world, cosmopolitanism, and overcoming parochial boundaries.

2. Methods

Narrative analysis is a qualitative form of data analysis. On the one hand, narrative methods must analyse text from the bottom-up and by considering the historical and geographical context of a particular border region (Prokkola, 2014). At the same time, narrative analysis for comparative enquiry must also be rigorous through close alignment between contributors as well as constant coordination. To guarantee this rigour, there was therefore also a top-down element insofar as all researchers participating in this analysis followed the same procedures regarding 1) choice of newspapers, 2) the time period to cover, 3) search terms to use, 4) software for coding, and a common coding framework.

2.1 Choice of newspapers

In this analysis, we have focused on regional newspapers that are distributed in regions that lie close to the border in question. Where there were several papers to choose from, the researchers prioritised geographical criteria to include those outlets whose geographical coverage most closely approximated the border region in question. Two newspapers that cover Germany's southeastern border region with both Poland and Czechia, namely the *Sächsische Zeitung* and the *Lausitzer Rundschau*, were chosen. Both cover parts of the Polish-German-Czech border region, with the former more focused on the Polish-German part and the latter on the whole trinational 'border triangle'.

The Halmstad University team opted to include three Danish newspapers. The Danish *Helsingor Dagblad* constitutes a 'natural pair' with the Swedish *Helsingborgs Dagblad*, as these two are based on each side of the narrowest part of the Öresund strait. The Swedish paper *Sydsvenskan* was chosen due to its dominance as the main print outlet for serious journalism in southern Sweden. However, the border-regional location of the capital Copenhagen makes it difficult to distinguish between national and local news. Therefore, one Copenhagen-based paper (*Berlingske*) and one local island newspaper, *Bornholms Tidende*, were included alongside *Helsingor Dagblad*.

In Poland, there are few significant regional papers. This is why Wrocław University researchers also included a national newspaper (*Gazeta Wyborcza*) with its regional add-on printed in Zielona Góra, in the western borderland with Germany, alongside the more regionally focused *Gazeta Lubuska*.

In some of our case study regions, there is no obvious political orientation of the newspapers in question, but in others one can discern such an orientation. The two Polish papers were selected not only based on geographical criteria but also based on their very divergent political message. *Gazeta Wyborcza* is a liberally oriented newspaper that was very critical of the PiS government and very supportive of the centre parties of the political spectrum. In contrast, after *Gazeta Lubuska* was taken over by a state-controlled petrol corporation Orlen in 2021, the editors were replaced, and the editorial line of the title shifted to represent the agenda of the ruling national populist coalition. In 2024, following the 2023 change of government in Poland, Orlen's board of directors as well as the chief editor of *Gazeta Lubuska*, were changed again, which was immediately followed by a clear and significant change in the political stance of *Gazeta Lubuska*. The analysis suggests that both papers feature mostly articles written from a nationwide perspective, marginalising or silencing the local or regional voices of the borderlanders. Both also published many interviews with politicians or experts who were representatives of the political orientation that is close to one of the respective newspaper's editorial line.

In the Slovak-Hungarian border region, no less than ten different news portals of Hungarian-language media in Slovakia were identified. As only a minority of the portals publicise data on their traffic and readership, a more comparable indication of their outreach is their number of followers on Facebook, the most popular social medium in the region. In mid-April 2024, the two portals with the most followers were *Új Szó* (94K) and *Felvidék.ma* (73K). These two were chosen because of this but also

because they are politically divergent: *Új Szó* tends to be critical of the incumbent governments of both Slovakia and Hungary and appears as a ‘mainstream’, centrist outlet. *Felvidék.ma* is the Hungarian government-supported outlet in Slovakia that has the widest readership by far, and it is generally right-wing. Regional editions of *SME* cover the Slovak-speaking part of the Slovak-Hungarian border region.

Two sources were chosen from Czechia. *Liberecký deník* is a regional newspaper published by VLTAVA LABE MEDIA a.s., which is one of the country’s largest publishing houses. There are more than 70 mutations based on the region of the newspaper. *Liberecký deník* is one of the most read newspapers in the country, with more than 1,850,000 readers reading it at least once a fortnight (*Liberecký deník*, 6 September 2024). Its popularity is connected to its long-term focus on regional news. *Idnes.cz* is the e-version of the MF Dnes newspaper, which is a part of the MAFRA Group, which was bought in June 2013 by the Czech politician, former prime minister and current leading opposition figure Andrej Babiš. The ownership of the newspaper (by the businessman and politician, who can be described as an oligarch) has, to a certain extent, influenced the opinions section of the newspaper, where the commentaries sometimes tend to take rather ‘nationalistic’ standpoints and show a rather critical stance vis-à-vis the Polish and German neighbours and the EU more broadly.

In the Danish-Swedish border region, the newspapers covered speak to parts of the political spectrum, with *Helsingborgs Dagblad* having centrist leanings, while *Sydsvenskan* is more conservative. On the Danish side, the spectrum ranges from cross-political *Helsingor Dagblad*, which covers several perspectives, to more conservative *Bornholms Tidende* to right-leaning *Berlingske*. As in Poland, the chosen newspapers tend towards national coverage. This was especially obvious during the 2024 European elections, when there were few attempts to link these elections to border regional questions. This tendency towards national coverage could be because the attitudes of Öresund residents towards the EU tend to match the national mood instead of having a specific ‘Öresund’ mindset.’

In cases where a region was covered by many regional papers with similar geographical reach and no obvious political alignment in the media landscape that would need to be accounted for, ready accessibility was also considered in the choice of newspaper outlets. This is the case for the regional newspapers chosen from Germany’s Baden-Württemberg region that borders on France.

The final selection of newspapers is as follows:

Team	Borderland	Newspaper selection
Halmstad University	Danish-Swedish border region	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Berlingske - Bornholms Tidende - Helsingor Dagblad - Helsingborgs Dagblad - Sydsvenskan
University of Strasbourg	Franco-German border region	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dernières Nouvelles d’Alsace - Le Républicain Lorrain - Saarbrücker Zeitung - Die Oberbadische
Wrocław University	Polish-German-Czech border region	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gazeta Wyborcza - Gazeta Lubuska - Sächsische Zeitung

Brunel University London Technical University of Liberec		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lausitzer Rundschau - Liberecký deník - IDnes.cz
Eötvös Loránd University Technical University of Liberec	Slovak-Hungarian border region	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Új Szó - Felvidék.ma - SME

2.2 Time period

All researchers covered the same timeframe between the 2019 and 2024 European elections. However, there was some flexibility to accommodate key regional events outside this timeframe such as the 2019 Aachen Treaty. In line with our conception of ‘kariotic time’, our focus was on key events, namely the 2019 and 2024 European elections as well as the first and second lockdowns during the Covid-19 pandemic.

2.3 Search strategy

During the search for sources, the search strategy underwent several iterations and revisions, as some search terms that yielded no helpful results were dropped and others added. The final search terms used by all included the following:

- eurosceptic* (the asterisk means that any word starting with eurosceptic would be included among the results, including Euroscepticism, Eurosceptics and eurosceptical)
- anti-EU, Brussels
- EU/European Union, Commission, ECJ/(European) Court of Justice (of the European Union)
- border/border region

In addition, individual teams used as search terms the specific names of regions such as Öresund, Lubuskie województwo or Alsace, as well as keywords from well-known local controversies such as conflict over the Turów coal mine in the Polish-German-Czech border region.

We used the search function of some newspapers directly, while others used subscription services such as Factiva and Genios. Reprints of press releases were discarded, as they are not useful for narrative analysis. Instead, most articles are editorial pieces, opinion pieces and original articles. In the end, we coded 1,244 articles:

Brunel University London Team: 160 articles

Eötvös Loránd University Team: 211 articles

Halmstad University Team: 150 articles

Technical University of Liberec Team: 138 articles

University of Strasbourg Team: 208 articles

Wrocław University Team: 377 articles

2.4 Software and coding framework

All researchers used either NVivo or Atlas.ti for coding. As the approach was qualitative rather than quantitative, coding was used as a way of identifying and flagging themes. They were grouped together for later analysis, combining substantive codes for queries and meta codes. A more rigid method of counting the frequency of a given theme would have been more common of quantitative content analysis, but such an approach would not have been suitable for tracing narratives.

From the start, we aimed to use a common coding framework to facilitate the later comparative analysis. At the same time, the common approach had to be flexible enough to allow for the emergence of themes from the bottom-up. This is because our narrative analysis of a novel research topic – the role of local border regional factors in shaping perceptions of the EU and Euroscepticism – was not yet very well-researched. In short, we did not have a large body of theory to draw that would have helped us anticipate any detailed findings.

Thus, the coding framework was developed iteratively. The common coding framework had 47 substantive themes [agriculture; border checks/controls; bordering; borderless Europe; commuter/commuting; cooperation; Covid; crime; crisis; cross-border; customs; debordering; duty to Europe; Eastern Europe(an/s); European Union Court of Justice (ECJ); election/campaign; elite/elitist; Erasmus, young people, students, children; EU; €/Euro; European Commission; European Parliament; Fortress Europe; **exit (e.g. Polesxit, Brexit...); idea of Europe, more than European Union; identity; (im)migration/immigrant(s); landscape; language; left-wing criticism of EU; local government; political parties/elections; populism; refugees; regional leaders' names; reparations; resentment; right-wing criticism of EU; Schengen; security; separateness; shopping; solidarity; togetherness; tourism; trust; Western Europe(an/s)]. These substantive codes came on top of meta-analytical codes which covered dimensions such as 'who speaks?' in the coded section (e.g. capacity in which they speak; if they are politicians, at what level of governance they operate; and what was their gender), name of newspaper, overall article theme, type of article, and date of publication.

3. Background

3.1 Introduction to cases

The Öresund region, for the purposes of B-SHAPES is defined as the territory covered by the organisation *Greater Copenhagen* (Copenhagen/Malmö and Helsingborg/Helsingør, Region Hovedstaden, Region Sjælland, Region Skåne and Region Halland), as well as part of the North Jutland Region. Historically, the region has been through territorial, political and cultural changes dating from the 17th century and onwards (Svensson and Nilson, 2023). While these changes had been conflictual, in the 19th century, a more conciliatory student movement – Scandinavism – emerged that highlighted political and cultural similarities and point out historical cases of unity. Nowadays, bilateral relations could be described as *both excellent and difficult* due to different policy stances on a few, but salient, issues. Denmark and Sweden are part of a Nordic and Scandinavian context, characterised by long-term collaboration, mutual understanding and a shared historical heritage. On the other hand, the cooperation has been strained by rivalry at the local and regional level and by policy differences concerning for example nuclear power, drug policy, immigration and Covid-19.

The French-German border region is defined here as Alsace, the bordering part of Lorraine, especially Moselle, which became German again along with Alsace during the 1870-1918 and 1940-1945 periods, and the bordering parts of the German states of Saarland and Baden-Württemberg. The border had long been an object of contestation even before the Second World War, as the Franco-German rivalry culminated in the 1870, 1914-18 and 1939-45 wars in which Alsace and parts of Lorraine changed hands. After the war, the Lorraine-born Minister Robert Schuman proposed launching an unprecedented cooperation together with Germany leading towards what became European Union. This watershed in relations did not only initiate a period of Franco-German integration and reconciliation; it also began the wider European integration project (Wassenberg, 2013). The border region has since become a symbol of an overall Franco-German friendship. This history and sense of European belonging are also made visible by the choice of Strasbourg (Alsace) as the seat of EU and Council of Europe institutions, most notably the European Parliament.

The Polish-German-Czech border region is defined here as the German state of Saxony (specifically the districts, or *Kreise*, Görlitz and Bautzen) as well as southern Brandenburg (*Kreis Spree-Neisse* and the city of Cottbus), the Polish Lubuskie region and parts of Dolnośląskie region, as well as the Czech Liberec region. This trinational border region looks back on a dramatic history of aggression, boundary changes and forced population movements that still forms part of living memory. It was at the (then) Czechoslovak and Polish borders that Nazi Germany's territorial aggression began in 1938 and 1939, which started the Second World War and Germany's brutal occupation period. After Germany lost the war, Czechoslovakia's border with Germany was restored, but Poland and Germany underwent severe border changes. These developments were followed by large-scale forced population movements of Germans and Poles (Urban, 2004). During the ensuing communist period, the borders between East Germany, Poland and Czechoslovakia were closed to varying degrees to the citizens in different time periods (Kowalke, 1997; Nothnagle, 1999). They were opened for visa-free travel after the end of communism and German unification in the early 1990s, and further relaxed with the EU enlargement of 2004 and Poland's and Czechia's accession to the Schengen area three years later.

Despite the small sizes of **Slovakia and Hungary**, their ca. 650km-long shared border is one of the longest intra-EU land boundaries (and the longest one of both countries). The focus for the purposes of B-SHAPES is on the border region's western parts. This is because Slovakia's ethnic Hungarian minority is more concentrated in the country's southwestern areas (Balogh and Pete 2018). This minority within Slovakia is a remnant of the post-First World War Treaty of Trianon of 1920, which transferred the Upper Hungary region, with areas that were predominantly ethnic Hungarian, to Czechoslovakia. During the Second World War, Hungary briefly occupied southern Slovakia. When

Czechoslovakia was recreated after the war, ethnic Hungarians were partially expelled, deported or underwent a Slovakisation process, but the number of Hungarians rose again in the 1950s. According to Slovakia's 2021 census, Hungarians constitute the country's largest ethnic minority, around 8% of the population. Since Slovakia's independence in 1993, issues related to the Hungarian minority have been the key factor in Slovak-Hungarian relations. These relations have fluctuated (experiencing low points around 1993–98 and 2008–11) but have overall improved in recent years. This is largely thanks to the general post-1998 democratisation of Slovakia and the cautious but ongoing official bilingualisation process, at least at the level of municipalities. Since both countries joined the EU in 2004 and the Schengen Area in 2007, cross-border mobility has intensified, with many bridges having been (re)built along the rivers Danube and Ipel'.

3.2 Who speaks?

The 'speakers' – or producers of narratives in the media – include experts, politicians at different levels of government, citizens, journalists, civil servants, and civil society actors. With this emphasis, our chosen newspapers generally gave little space to the voices of young borderlanders.

One observation made by the Wrocław team is that the borderlanders' voices in both selected Polish newspapers were published only occasionally. They were rather interpellated by the newspapers to speak instead of giving the publishing space to the citizens. By using authorised voices close to the ideology, sympathies, and interests of the given newspaper, borderlands narratives were manufactured and projected top-down from the centres of power in the country. Similarly, in the media analysis of the Slovak-Hungarian border region, among op-eds and commentaries, very few represent readers' opinions.

Researchers also paid special attention to the gender dimension, in coding the gender of the 'speaker', or the producer of a particular narrative, whenever this was discernible. Analyses of these meta codes showed that, in most border regions, male voices prevail to varying degrees among the speakers. In the Franco-German border region, both male and female journalists were well represented, with 38% female journalists. In the Slovak-Hungarian border region, the majority of the articles were written by men and about men, but many also by and on women.

In the Danish-Swedish border region, a further distinction can be drawn between different categories of speakers. For example, among local politicians, males made up 91% of the coded references and females 9%, and there were no instances of unclear genders in the material. Among regional politicians, 89% of the codes went to males and 11% to females. However, at the national level, 64% of references were from male politicians and 36% from females. A similar pattern emerges in the German media from the Polish-German-Czech border region. Here, the most prominent categories of speakers are journalists and politicians at all levels, including EU, national, regional and local levels, followed by economic actors and civil society actors. In all these categories, there is an imbalance in the gender of the speaker, with 56% of all coded reference being made by men, 25% by women and the remainder by speakers whose gender is unclear. Only in one category – EU politicians – does the share of references uttered by a female outweigh that uttered by a male, notably because the Green MEP Anna Cavazzini – an outspoken critic of the Turów coal mine, which featured prominently in the German media narratives from the Polish-German-Czech border region – was quoted frequently. Similar to the Danish-Swedish case, at the level of national politicians, there is near parity, with 44% of the clear references spoken by women and 56% spoken by men. Conversely, at the local and regional levels, male politicians' voices are far more prominent than female ones, at 86% and 90% of the clear references respectively, though this is commensurate with the overrepresentation of men in local and regional politicians in the region.

Aware of these imbalances, the authors took care to ensure that our research does not replicate the silencing of voices. When analysing and quoting the material, researchers ensured that examples of narratives produced by people of different genders, as well as those holding different functions, were included. The result, with regard to the gender dimension, cannot therefore be commensurate with a 50/50 split, but it is commensurate with the representation of genders in the material. As noted above, there is little representation of citizens' voices, and particularly of young borderlanders' voices, because citizens were quoted rather rarely. Their voices will be given more space in an upcoming (January 2025) report on the results of the interviews with party candidates and the focus groups with borderland residents.

4. Characterisations and Depictions of the Neighbours

Our first step was to analyse how the respective neighbours are characterised in the media within our case study border regions. There are three main narratives in depictions of these neighbours: 1) friendship, neighbourship and kinship, 2) conflict and rivalry, 3) central versus local. In some of these narratives, there are latent links to the European Union, but mostly the focus is on bi- or trilateral relations or on local connections.

4.1 Friendship, neighbourship and kinship

In some media narratives, the neighbours are depicted positively. This is most obvious in the narratives from the Franco-German border region. Here, the 'Franco-German friendship' has a strikingly prominent place in the media narratives. It features in many articles and symbolises the idea of a dynamic evolution in cross-border relations: no article looks at Franco-German relations without mentioning the Franco-German friendship. There are some regional variations, insofar as the friendship theme is more prominent between Alsace and Baden than it is between Lorraine and Saarland. The *Oberbadische*, for example, ran the headline 'Living friendship with French people' (*Die Oberbadische*, 26 October 2023) to talk about the return of French cross-border and Erasmus students after the Covid-19 crisis. A similarly strong connection is felt on the Alsatian side. An example of this reflex for friendship can be found even during times of crisis, e.g. when German police apparently overreacted to prohibited activities during Covid-19, but this was depicted with understanding in the French press (*Dernières Nouvelles d'Alsace*, 16 April 2020): 'Excesses of zeal, or errors of assessment, exist on both sides of the Rhine.' In addition to this friendship, which is related explicitly to the European integration project (see below), there is a visible theme of 'kinship' on both sides of the Rhine, a sense of common shared history. On the French side, a sense of pride of a German-centred local heritage is visible (*Dernières Nouvelles d'Alsace*, 17 August 2020). Slightly further away from this centre of European integration, in Saarland, the idea of having neighbours rather than a foreign country is also discernible (*Républicain Lorrain*, 2 October 2023; *Saarbrücker Zeitung*, 5 September 2023): 'The aim of this march is to build bonds of friendship with our German neighbours,' and:

'Deepening cooperation in healthcare is particularly important to me. We have to get to the point where people in the border area can take advantage of the care offered by the neighboring country without discrimination,' says Gillo, referring to the collaboration between the Völklingen Heart Center and the clinic in Forbach. 'It works there. We want to expand that.' The debates about cross-border emergency operations have already come closer. It just depends on little things. Gillo: 'We can develop Europe very well at the border. Concrete offers and support for the people in this region are better than symbolic politics.' (*Saarbrücker Zeitung*, 5 September 2023)

In the Polish-German-Czech border region, one can detect some positive narratives with an emphasis on neighbourship (though not necessarily friendship). Both the *Lausitzer Rundschau* and the *Sächsische Zeitung* avoid stereotypical depictions of Czechs and Poles. A substantial share of the reporting is devoted to cooperative initiatives and to the cultural richness of the neighbours. The word 'neighbours' is used frequently. There are emphases on the 'border triangle' or Lusatia being cultural regions with many historical and cultural connections, and the term 'the region' is sometimes used to cover the entire border region. Similarly, one Polish paper, *Gazeta Wyborcza*, did not display any anti-German sentiment. This could have arisen, for example, during discussions about the Polish government's efforts to obtain reparations for wartime losses in the Second World War. In contrast, Germans were portrayed positively, often accompanied by praise for the European Union, of which Germany is a part.

In the Danish-Swedish border region, one can discern a long-standing kinship insofar as Denmark and Sweden are part of a Nordic and Scandinavian context, characterised by long-term collaboration, mutual understanding and a shared historical heritage, as expressed by a Eurosceptic politician:

I would like us to look at how the Nordic countries can stand more together in the world. Yes, the more uncertain the world is, it is even important that we have a compass which means that we do not create more uncertainty. The Nordic countries have some (joint) values. (*Bornholms Tidende*, 3 June 2022).

In the Slovak-Hungarian border region, the overall thrust of the media narratives is an impression of a borderland where relations are 'normalising'. While there are some negative narratives touching, for example, on swine flu and traffic congestion, the overall narrative is one of a region where cross-border ties are growing, Interreg projects are being implemented, and cross-border investments are taking place with or without external support (*Új Szó*, 6 February 2020). In addition, people are depicted as travelling to places near and far, and regularly crossing the border for shopping and other cross-border activities.

4.2 Conflict and rivalry

In the Polish-German-Czech border region, narratives of conflict exist side by side with narratives of neighbourship. In general, the Polish and German sides are very focused on one another. In contrast, Czechs are mostly presented neutrally as players in the Turów controversy, which is also what the Czech narratives focus on (*Idnes.cz*, 8 February 2023).

In contrast to *Gazeta Wyborcza*, *Gazeta Lubuska* constructed a consistently negative narrative about Germans after the changes to its editorial board in 2021. Germans are often portrayed in the context of an autocratic EU power, where Berlin, as the capital of Germany, is also presented as the main centre of power and the dispenser of orders to EU bodies ('The only option for now is the principle of the empty chair, that is the blockage of the EU and its decisions ..., as long as Berlin and Brussels will stop blackmailing, offending, and blocking the EU funding for Poland', *Gazeta Lubuska*, 15 October 2021). The German national interest, which is portrayed as contrary to Polish interests, is mentioned frequently. Germany's refusal to discuss war reparations is interpreted as a refusal to take responsibility for the Nazi period and its crimes. In summary, for *Gazeta Lubuska*, Germany equates to Berlin, and Berlin equates to Brussels ('We see, today more than ever, that Brussels is Berlin, only in Belgium. Just in order to hide the fact', *Gazeta Lubuska*, 28 May 2022). This leads to the observation that the negative attitude towards Germany is also an expression of Euroscepticism present in *Gazeta Lubuska*. However, the editorial team changed again in 2024 – after this change the negative narrative about Germany disappeared from the pages of *Gazeta Lubuska*.

Similarly, in both German newspapers from the Polish-German-Czech border region, one can detect a narrative of the Polish side riding roughshod over its neighbours, e.g. during the Turów controversy and a mass fish death in the river Odra in 2022 (*Lausitzer Rundschau*, 23 January 2023). Here, the Polish side is accused of a lack of neighbourliness and even deviousness. For example, the mayor of Zittau is quoted as criticising the Polish position on Turów on the grounds that this is insufficiently neighbourly: 'There are rules that you do not break. One of these is: you do not harm your neighbour.' (*Lausitzer Rundschau*, 23 January 2023). Somewhat similar, yet softer, narrative appeared also in Czech media space (*Liberecký deník*, 5 February 2022).

In the Slovak-Hungarian border region, one can detect some narratives of conflict. These include narratives of certain Slovak politicians drawing parallels between Crimea and Csallóköz [a Hungarian-dominated region in southwestern Slovakia] (*Új Szó*, 25 July 2019b). However, these reports were

quickly dismissed, as ‘the Csallóköz is not an autonomous republic, Hungary is not Russia, and Slovakia and Hungary are EU members.’ Additionally, ‘there is not much air left for revisionist policies in a borderless Europe and serious politicians are not really talking about them, as this would be against everything the EU stands for’. Some minor irritations occurred in the summer of 2019, when several articles (*Új Szó*, 25 July 2019a) reported the arrival of African swine flu in Slovakia. It was presumed that the disease had made it there through wild boars from Hungary, where it had already been present. Hence, most people were banned from the surroundings of the settlements between Košice and the border, justified by a desire not to interfere in the wild boars’ mobility patterns (*Új Szó*, 2 September 2019). Also, a few articles appeared about some people trying to cross the border illegally, such as 16 young Afghans at Štúrovo (*Új Szó*, 19 August 2019). Finally, in early 2020 several articles followed the traffic congestions and diversions caused by protesting truckers who for a week or so were blocking roads and borders across Slovakia (*Új Szó*, 13 January 2020).

There are no visible signs of such a conflictual narrative in the French-German border context, which highlights the importance of the ‘friendship’ narrative described above. Likewise, in the Danish-Swedish context, no narrative of conflict could be detected. The imbalance of interventionism between the two countries, with Denmark being much more protectionist, has, however, been pointed out as potential grounds for conflicts to potentially emerge; the border is to a larger extent recognised as a potential source of conflict (Sohn 2023). As we can read in the Danish *Berlingske* for instance: “‘I think in principle that we in Denmark should decide the extent, layout and length of our controls at the borders ourselves,’ says Jeppe Kofod.” (*Berlingske*, 20 June 2019).

4.3 Central versus local

In the Danish-Swedish border region, one can detect a certain rivalry at the local and regional levels. In fact, at the local level, the process around the creation of the Greater Copenhagen Association in 2016, as a revamped version of the earlier Öresund Committee into the organisation *Greater Copenhagen*, illustrates the importance of local power asymmetries and how policy issues can spill over into local cross-border integration efforts. The creation took place in what turned out to be bad timing: it started to operate in the aftermath of the 2015 refugee situation/crisis. Up until then, at the national level, Sweden had a more welcoming asylum policy since the late 1990s and early 2000s, a time during which Danish policy became increasingly strict. This difference in policy attitudes led to strains manifested during this crisis and the introduction of border controls (Svensson 2023). This was mirrored in differential approaches to the Covid-19 pandemic. Paradoxically, over the past few years, support for a common regional identity among policy actors seems to have strengthened, while mobility across the border is to a larger extent recognised as a potential source of conflict (Svensson 2023). These conflicts, and the fear of damage to trust, are visible in the analysed media material as well:

The Öresund region can still be a resounding success. But then Swedish and Danish decision-makers must understand each other. Show understanding for each other. And trust each other. (*Sydsvenskan*, 19 April 2020).

In the Polish-German border region, *Gazeta Lubuska*, as already shown, presents ‘Berlin’ as a shorthand for German and EU power, and pits this against Polish sovereignty. In the *Lausitzer Rundschau* and the *Sächsische Zeitung*, too, one can detect a ‘Blame Warsaw’ narrative, though this is less directly linked to the European Union. For example, in response to the swine flu outbreak, some on the German side suggested building fences on both sides of the border rivers Odra and Nisa, ‘But it soon emerged that this idea was not well received in the Warsaw government.’ Germany’s Agriculture Minister suggested that Germany or the EU would pay for this, ‘but Warsaw would not even agree to this’ (*Lausitzer Rundschau*, 26 March 2021). There are other examples where ‘Warsaw’ is presented as intransigent (*Sächsische Zeitung*, 4 December 2019). Still, a clear difference is drawn between national

and local politicians. For example, ‘The collaboration of Polish local politicians on the trilateral memorandum [to demand improved cross-border rail infrastructure] shows: in contrast to the Polish central government, there is definitely an interest in a proper railway line *in the region*.’ (*Sächsische Zeitung*, 4 November 2019, emphasis added). Distant capitals are not only contrasted with local politicians, who are presented – and present themselves – as having a finer understanding of local needs, but also with local people. For example, there was some coverage of the anti-German propaganda of the Polish PiS party during the 2023 election campaign, but ‘A Pole who has been living in Görlitz for a long time, thinks that many Poles are annoyed by this. ‘They want to do business with Germans, they need German tourists.’’ (*Sächsische Zeitung*, 11 October 2023).

In the Franco-German border region, one can likewise detect a discrepancy between the decisions taken at the central level and the reality of cross-border life. The following testimony comes from a German mother living in France who sends her children to a binational school in Germany, highlighting the idea that there is indeed a cross-border reality that is not understood in the capitals:

‘People from Berlin know nothing about our cross-border region. We’re the ones who live here, it’s not up to them to decide for our region. I’m ashamed to be German,’ says Cosima, sad ‘that it’s come to this. They think we’re lepers because we live in Moselle [Lorraine, former part of Elsass-Lothringen], but the virus is on both sides of the border, and so are the variants. Instead of wasting all this money on thousands of useless tests, it would be better to put all this energy into vaccines.’ (*Le Républicain Lorrain*, 5 March 2021).

To summarise, narratives of friendship and conflict can coexist within the same border region. At the same time, the central versus local narrative juxtaposes policymakers in central governments, and sometimes at the European level, with local politicians and populations. In these narratives, the local level is nearly always presented as the one closest to borderlanders’ concerns. However, it can also be a source of powerlessness in conflicts and problems that go beyond local issues, as will be shown below using the examples of the Turów controversy or the question of the external EU border. The contrast between local and central levels of decision-making is also important for our next narrative theme – bordering and debordering – which crucially pits decisions taken in the capitals against their effects on the ground in the border regions.

5. Bordering and Debordering

The concepts of bordering and debordering involve a contrast between a trend towards boundary-making and fortifying borders in at least some policy areas on the one hand, and a trend towards diminishing the boundary role of a border in at least some areas on the other (cf. Popescu, 2012). In European border regions, this juxtaposition reflects a dynamic interplay of historical, political, and socio-economic factors, as exemplified in the four distinct regions under study. One can detect some overarching themes: one of these is the idea of bordering because of crisis. For example, in bordering responses to migration or Covid-19, one can discern states' reflex towards presenting bordering as a crisis management tool or as a tool of (auto)immunological protection. Nevertheless, as our media analysis shows, there is often considerable local resistance to such measures that rest on a long-standing reality of borders being invisible to most borderlanders. When that reality is disrupted, there are calls for debordering and a return to borders being largely invisible, at least to the population segments in question. However, in other contexts, one can detect clear support for bordering, which tends to be stronger when it affects not oneself but rather others.

5.1 Bordering

Bordering, the concept of tightening or advocating for the closure of borders, emerges prominently in European border regions, particularly in response to crises or conflicts. As observed through the media analysis, bordering represents a reactive stance often adopted by member states or regional entities faced with socio-economic, environmental, or political challenges. The most glaring recent example is the Covid-19 pandemic, which precipitated widespread border closures across Europe in efforts to contain the virus' spread. However, there are other examples, such as actions or calls to fortify external borders, like that between Poland and Belarus, to protect the EU from unwelcome illegal migrants, as well as calls for bordering to counter crime. Smaller themes, such as responses to an outbreak of swine flu, are more localised, so that the decision was made here to focus on the three most overarching themes related to bordering.

The media coverage underscores how these crises catalyse bordering responses that shape regional dynamics and governance strategies, navigating the delicate balance between regional autonomy and supranational cooperation. However, the newspaper coverage also shows how measures from the top-down are received on the ground, where one can observe a differentiation: when bordering affects 'us', it is often resisted, but when it affects mostly others (e.g. migrants), then it can be tolerated or even welcomed.

Migration: narratives of the (in)securitisation of borders

While our search criteria meant that we captured few articles covering immigration from outside the EU, articles do touch on the political discourse around external EU border controls in the context of national and European elections. One narrative related to migration links strongly with the securitisation of borders, suggesting that migrants, asylum-seekers and people smugglers threaten the security of the EU and of individual member states. In this narrative, bordering strategies such as border controls are presented as a remedy to make Europe safe from these threats. This said, the perceived threat from migration emerges at different points in time in different regions – with the watershed moment in the Danish-Swedish border region occurring in 2015, while the peak of the Polish media coverage was in 2021 and in Germany in 2023. This fact alone illustrates that crises such as the much-trumpeted 'migration crisis' play out differently in different localities, but it also suggests an element of arbitrariness in when an event is perceived or constructed as a crisis (cf. Fassin, 2024).

For example, border checks and border controls have dominated Danish-Swedish Öresund relations for the better part of a decade. The watershed moment was the so-called refugee crisis of 2015, when

more than one million refugees entered Europe under what were largely perceived as unorderly conditions. Many of those had Sweden as their ultimate preferred destination. The Swedish government initially upheld a relatively generous asylum system, but in November 2015 it did a policy U-turn and introduced strict border controls, along with other measures to deter refugees (Scarpa and Schierup, 2018). In 2024, too, one can detect a narrative that the external borders would be needed to be secured so that the internal borders can be kept open. This demand for external security, coupled to internal freedom of movement, featured in coverage of interviews with, or debates between, party representatives, and appeared in both countries. One Swedish example is illustrative:

We have several hundred Swedish employees in Helsingör municipality and it is incredibly important that free movement is preserved. But to maintain it, we must strengthen the EU's external borders, says Birgitte Bergman, Konservative Folkeparti (*Helsingör Dagblad*, 30 March 2024).

In the case of Denmark, the same narrative exists but is also coupled with one issue related to the internal border, a demand for permanent ID controls and a permanent border police among the fringe of the political party spectrum:

Along with permanent border control, a permanent border police must be established, says Inger Støjberg, who envisions around 100 officers who will only focus on border tasks. There have been regular reports that it is difficult to get enough officers willing to work as border guards. DR broadcast a series of reports on the border police earlier in 2024, where the lack of staff was revealed. But Støjberg is not nervous that there may be a shortage of personnel. Border control must be a separate track in the police training, the draft says, and then the job will be different from the current border officers: - Much more will be put into the task. It is not a matter of just checking passports. There must be a focus on cross-border crime, which is a significant part of the crime we see in Denmark, she says. (*Helsingör Dagblad*, 2 June 2024).

The narrative of the (in)securitisation of borders continued into 2024, with EU election campaign paying attention to external border control (see below) and also how high Swedish crime rates continues to be seen as a threat to Denmark: 'An effective fight against drug trafficking is not only necessary to curb addiction and break organized crime, it is also a cornerstone in the defense of free movement and the internal market.' (*Helsingborgs Dagblad*, 4 June 2024).

The narrative of bordering as a securitisation measure is even more dramatic in Poland. From the summer of 2021, there had been rising numbers of migrants who were imported to Belarus by the security service and then pushed to the EU borders. New types of re-bordering were tested by Poland on its eastern border with Belarus: territorial states of exceptions, criminalisation of 'crimes of solidarity', attempts to legalise pushbacks of people on the move who demanded asylum rights, or, ultimately, walling of borders. In the *Gazeta Lubuska's* narratives, re-bordering of the Belarussian border is described in terms of defending Poland, Europe, the EU, and the West and NATO more generally against Belarussian and Russian proxy wars. The slogan that Poland protects not only itself but also the whole Europe, repeated by Law and Justice's politicians, is quoted with approval time and time again ('It is about the security of Poland and the security and stability of the EU', quote from Polish PM Mateusz Morawiecki, *Gazeta Lubuska*, 21 September 2021; 'It is an assault both on the Polish border and the EU border', quote from Morawiecki, *Gazeta Lubuska*, 23 September 2021; 'The protection of our border is also the protection of the Eastern wing of the EU and NATO', quote from Morawiecki, *Gazeta Lubuska*, 10 November 2021). This service by Polish border guards and the army

and efforts such as the construction of the border fence are presented as deserving of support and recognition from the rest of Europe. In the case of *Gazeta Wyborcza*, more liberal sentiments based on human rights of migrants are mixed and confined by the principles of *Realpolitik* which justify the securitization and condemn the naivety of idealists (e.g. ‘Morality opens the door to populists’, title of the interview with John Dalhuisen from European Stability Initiative think tank’, *Gazeta Wyborcza*, 7 March 2020).

Poland’s border with Belarus coincides with the external border of the EU, but as open borders within the EU and within the Schengen Area hinge on bordering at the external borders, there are also examples of calls for bordering at our case study borders, which are intra-EU borders. For example, in Germany in 2023, many national and regional politicians from the centre-right CDU, including the prime minister of Saxony, demanded that the German government notify the European Commission of its intention to establish border controls at the borders with Poland and Czechia. One example is the Görlitz district administrator Stephan Meyer, who said ‘As the district of Görlitz, we are always affected particularly strongly and particularly early by the increasing number of refugees due to our proximity to the border.’ (*Sächsische Zeitung*, 5 November 2022). The German Federal government long resisted border controls, but it introduced such controls at the borders with Poland, Czechia and Switzerland in October 2023, citing the high level of migrant smuggling activity. To name but one example, a local politician praised these measures, echoing the narrative of the securitisation of borders being an effective measure:

We know from conversations with federal police officers that the controls at the borders with Poland and the Czech Republic have a dual effect. On the one hand, illegal migration is curbed significantly, and on the other hand, wanted people can be successfully apprehended... We need border controls until the EU’s external borders can be protected effectively. (*Sächsische Zeitung*, 4 May 2024).

More generally, by 2024, the German media from the Polish-German-Czech border region had become very supportive of bordering. Several articles together develop a securitisation narrative of border controls as a successful measure against people trafficking (e.g. *Sächsische Zeitung*, 4 May 2024).

In *Gazeta Lubuska*, Germany’s decision to close the border was described as unnecessary and exaggerated because Poland was able to tackle illegal immigration through its territory (‘German controls paralyze Lubuskie borderland’ (title), *Gazeta Lubuska*, 7 November 2023). At the same time, starting in the summer of 2021, the newspaper began reproducing the very consistent impression that borders in Europe are under siege, that they must be securitised and re-walled, and that member states should take back control over their borders. This results in a contradiction between the defence of Poles’ freedom of movement and the support for national control over border policies, which may lead to the loss of this freedom. This double standard in supporting some aspects of bordering but not others can also be seen in Germany. Here, there was much support for Germany’s introduction of border checks at the borders with Czechia and Poland in response to illegal migration in 2023. In contrast, during the Covid-19 border closures instigated by the Polish and Czech governments in 2020, there was much opposition on the German side, as will be shown below.

Interestingly, border closures to protect a country from immigrants have been mentioned in the Franco-German regional media, but in a highly critical context. Helene Maillasson, a bilingual Franco-German journalist at the *Saarbrucker Zeitung*, describes the French presidential elections in 2022 and the issues at stake for cross-border life between Lorraine and Saarland. The article states that:

Le Pen, for example, is in favour of the return of border controls to prevent immigration into France. Unlike Macron, who together with former German Chancellor Angela Merkel (CDU) launched the reconstruction fund following the Corona crisis, Le Pen does not believe in a common financial policy. (Saarbrucker Zeitung, 5 April 2022).

This description is not neutral, as the journalist highlights the danger of nationalism for cross-border life. In other words, the main narrative we can find in the regional media from the Franco-German border region in which border closures as a securitisation measure are mentioned, is one of the journalist's opposition to these proposals.

Impact of Covid-19: narratives of auto(immunological) bordering

The narratives produced during Covid-19 touch on the narrative of crisis in Europe, as the Coronavirus in Europe was first detected in Italy and then spread rapidly across Europe. They also touch on the narrative of immunological crisis: intra-EU and intra-Schengen border closures were presented as means of protecting the body politic of individual member states from the pathogen, which was presented as an outside threat. New techniques for bordering were invented, e.g. through COVID-19 passports, quarantines, and measures to distinguish the infected from the healthy and to differentiate freedom of movement for various categories of people ('New restrictions in Germany starting today', *Gazeta Lubuska*, 1 December 2020). Thus, during the pandemic, borders underwent a transformation: from bridge to fence to filter.

Justifications and approving narratives could be found among our media narratives. For example, in some Czech articles on the initial phase of the pandemic, there were testimonies of politicians blaming cross-border commuters for importing the virus from Germany (*Liberecky denik*, 13 May 2021). Likewise, according to the Danish Prime Minister Mette Frederiksen, 'My position on border control is the same as it has been throughout. In the epidemic, where we need border control, we must of course have border control' (*Helsingor Dagblad*, 25 February 2021). Some Slovak Hungarians were also reported as supporting the border closures, but only one article explicitly claimed this (*j Szo*, 14 March 2020), and it represented the voice of only two citizens.

Thus, supportive narratives existed. Still, in most narratives the position on Covid-19 measures was one of opposition to the border closures. Thus, in the Franco-German border region, out of the 316 selected articles concerning borders, there was not one article in which the prospect of a border closure, for example during the Covid-19 crisis, was presented as a positive or reassuring event.

In every single border region, local media highlighted the plight of borderlanders (Sarmiento-Mirwaldt, Svensson et al., 2024). As noted above, border controls have long dominated Danish-Swedish resund relations, but during the Covid-19 pandemic, the situation intensified. In the Czech media, Covid-19-related border closures did not attract much media attention, although this hugely affected the daily lives of individuals residing on all three sides of the borders, particularly cross-border commuters, especially Poles commuting to Czechia for work in industrial zones (especially in manufacturing car parts). These individuals found themselves affected disproportionately by the closures. Similarly, in Poland, *Gazeta Lubuska* reported on protests of borderlanders provoked by the border closures, especially commuting workers who lost their incomes. On the German side, too, the border closures

were covered largely through the issue of commuting, and the narrative in question is almost entirely devoted to the downsides of bordering:

The Corona crisis ... shows, how strongly the border regions have grown together in the last few years. Cross-border commuting has become the new normal for many. In agriculture, the crisis reminds us of the importance of seasonal workers. Paradoxically, they are Europe's last frequent flyers. They cannot afford to isolate at home due to Corona. (*Sächsische Zeitung*, 2 May 2020).

In the Franco-German border region, the situation of cross-border workers was addressed in all the newspapers studied. While it was to be expected that this issue would be raised in the context of the Covid-19 crisis, which initially led to fairly tight border closures that were then gradually eased, it was also raised outside the context of a crisis. Thus, the fate of cross-border workers was the subject of many French and German articles because different work rules prevailed in different countries at the height of the crisis.

At the start of the crisis, on the advice of the Koch Institute [...], employers forced Alsatian border workers, who were considered to be at risk, to go home within the hour. Border workers have since been able to return to work, but the situation remains complicated. Their patience is sorely tested: 'There is sometimes a two- to three-hour wait to cross the border with the controls in place, both in the north of Alsace and in central Alsace. It's unmanageable. We need to open more crossing points,' he suggests opening up the old truck lanes at border crossings where this is possible. 'Once there, border workers are singled out in certain companies. There they are not allowed to eat with their work colleagues' ... 'Elsewhere, one company wanted to introduce night work just for them, so that they wouldn't bump into their German colleagues.' (*Dernières Nouvelles d'Alsace*, 22 April 2020).

In the Slovak-Hungarian border region, the regional media published several articles and letters to the Slovak and Hungarian governments appealing to them to ease the restrictions. One aspect of this was the difficulties faced by cross-border commuters, e.g. in the divided border city Komárno/Komárom. Here, the border crossing was closed, and 'now, Slovak citizens working on the other side had to travel over 100km extra' (*Felvidék.ma*, 19 March 2020). Likewise, one article (*Felvidék.ma*, 4 May 2020) reported on the civic initiative 'At home with our heart,' which was strongly against the border closures. As the president of the initiative said: 'we see no reason for not lifting the border barriers... when cross-border workers in the immediate borderland can cross without any controls.' Moreover, 'with the border closures, many of us got isolated from our relatives, tearing apart entire families.'

In other border regions, too, the repercussions of the border closures for citizens in general, such as students or families were raised. Indeed, the most emotion was displayed in relation to families that were separated, including children of parents living on the other side. Families were disrupted by the border closures, and there were reports of this at the Slovak-Hungarian border (*Új Szó*, 15 May 2020), the Franco-German border, as captured in articles headlines such as 'When love collides with borders' (*DNA*, 28 May 2020) and 'Binational couples will be able to reunite' (*DNA*, 27 September 2020) and in the Danish-Swedish border region:

My son and I live 35 kilometres from each other. It is a 35-minute journey. There are no reasonable reasons why we cannot meet. When children are denied access to their parents, it is a violation of the Convention on the Rights of the Child, says Maria Frantzén Sanko. According to the ninth paragraph of

the Convention on the Rights of the Child, children have the right to live with their parents - and to maintain contact with both. - It is a convention that Sweden violates on a daily basis. (*Sydsvenskan*, 12 January 2021).

In the Franco-German press, articles were very numerous and very diverse, but they all pointed in the same direction, regardless of the intensity of the Covid-19 crisis at the time of publication: in this cross-border region, drawing a border is artificial and does not effectively combat the disease:

In Freiburg, two students from the Haut-Rhin region have been forced to interrupt the six weeks of engineering school they were studying at the University of Strasbourg. 'On Monday evening, the board of the University of Freiburg asked students who had spent the weekend in the Haut-Rhin to stay with us for 14 days. I can understand that the German authorities are taking precautions, but it's not very pleasant to be sidelined in this way,' says the 21-year-old student (*Dernières Nouvelles d'Alsace*, 10 March 2020).

In most of these narratives, there is little mention of the EU level, indicating a more localised focus. One exception is the Danish-Swedish border region, where the Swedish government decided to examine various legal means to make border checks permanent. The discussions continued to focus on the factual effects of these, often citing persons claiming the policy measure to be ineffective. However, it is noticeable how many more references were made to the legality (or non-legality) of these in the light of EU law. A court case by the South Sweden chamber of Commerce contributed to this aspect moving up the agenda.

The government has been in a hurry to come up with an alternative to the border police's constant presence at the Öresund. The reason is that the Supreme Administrative Court may soon label the border controls as illegal. - They violate Swedish law and EU law. That is why we request a legal review, says HStephan MÜchler, CEO of the South Swedish Chamber of Commerce. (*Helsingborgs Dagblad*, 9 February 2023).

A criticism of the EU's handling of the pandemic can be found in May 2020 in the media from the Slovak-Hungarian region. The charge was that 'Brussels had been asleep in the first four weeks of the pandemic... Italy was first helped by China, Russia, and Cuba. Where was Brussels, and the other [member states]...?' The EU subsequently woke up, but 'its initially announced €1 trillion crisis management fund has now shrunk to €540bn... while macroeconomists rate the economic damage caused at around €2–3 trillion'. Meanwhile, trust in the EU declined: 'Brussels is just watching how the Schengen system is collapsing, as [member states] are closing internal borders, at the same time as the EU's four freedoms are vanishing...' (*Új Szó*, 5 May 2020).

In short, while one can detect some limited narratives supportive of a conception of borders as autoimmunological borders, bottom-up responses from the border regions were overwhelmingly hostile to border closures. Stories of the plight of commuters in particular, but also of families suffering from these restrictions, were very common.

Crime: more narratives of the (in)securitisation of borders

Another area that serves to illustrate narratives of support and opposition to bordering is crime, such as theft, (people) smuggling and organised crime. These narratives are more localised and could be found mostly in the Danish-Swedish border region and on the German side of the Polish-German-Czech border region.

In 2017, Denmark used the Schengen Border Code possibility to conduct internal border controls citing crime as a reason. In November 2019, this turned into a regular practice, leading to high media coverage on both sides. News articles focused on the time this would take (which could be seen as little or much) and whether this could be expected to have effect. On the opinion pages, the tone was more emotional, and often critical towards the measure.

Politics that is merely symbolic means we continue to have border controls on the Swedish side of the (Oresund) strait. Border checks that in one year led to 10 million checks, but only two found weapons. It is probably the least effective police effort in Sweden when it comes to finding weapons. Nevertheless, the Danish government now wants to introduce border controls towards Sweden. Because according to the Danish government, criminals come from Sweden to Denmark. And it does. While the motorcycle gangs and Black Cobras came from Denmark to Sweden. Like the weapons and drugs that continue to come to Malmö and Sweden from the continent despite border controls. Because people move in our region. Those who want it and those who don't. The problem with border controls is that they negatively affect ordinary citizens, but border controls have no effect on organised gangs. (*Sydsvenskan*, 12 October 2019).

However, the media coverage also included positive perspectives or counterarguments from policymakers, such as references to positive effects of border controls on crime.

There has previously been cooperation and connections between Danish and Swedish criminals, but what is interesting, new and worrying is the direct Swedish connection in several of the murder cases. The current conflicts and the Swedish connection emphasise that organised crime cannot be limited by customs officers and passport control. And when a bridge is built over the Øresund, the criminals see it as a business opportunity to expand the market and send weapons, drugs and personnel over the bridge or by boat. (*Berlingske*, 14 January 2022).

In the media from the German side of the Polish-German-Czech border region, a narrative establishes a clear link between open borders and crime. There are many examples of this, but one paragraph sums the narrative up clearly:

After the abolition of border controls at the Oder [Odra] and Neisse [Nisa],¹ the number of car thefts had shot up. This is because criminals, in contrast to police and prosecutors, who continue to be bound by judicial constraints, can exploit open borders in full for their own ends. Berlin and Brandenburg were like self-service shops for them. (*Lausitzer Rundschau*, 19 November 2019).

There were a few calls for re-bordering in the shape of temporary border controls in response to crime, e.g. from the CDU candidate for the regional parliament Tilmann Havenstein: 'We need more Federal Police visibly present. Such measures must have a deterrent effect.' (*Lausitzer Rundschau*, 22 August 2019). However, in contrast to earlier enthusiastic calls for bordering to combat swine flu, calls for rebordering in response to theft were limited and muted, and there was much emphasis on other crime-fighting mechanisms such as cross-border police cooperation as well as technology in the shape of cameras (*Lausitzer Rundschau*, 6 July 2020).

¹ Henceforth these rivers will be referred to as Odra and Nisa.

Thus, in contrast to bordering in the context of Covid-19, one can detect some narratives that are supportive of bordering in response to crime. These narratives chime with the broader narrative of the securitisation of borders. In this, it is important to highlight a difference in who the target is of bordering measures. During the Covid-19 pandemic, at least initially, broad brushstrokes measures were aimed at everybody. When large numbers of people, such as commuters are affected, or emotional bonds such as those between families divided by a border, come into play, resistance to border closures is likely. In contrast, when the target is migrants or criminals, it is easier for borderlanders to support such targeted closures.

5.2 Debordering

The analysis under the 'bordering' theme has already shown that, in some instances such as Covid-19, there was massive opposition to attempts at (re-)bordering. In a sense, such resistance could itself be conceived as debordering. This said, one can also conceive of debordering more actively, in the style of Fritz Scharpf's (1998) distinction between positive and negative integration, where negative integration means removing barriers (or here, resisting bordering) and positive integration means actively building new connections. In this sense, debordering represents more than the mere 'disappearance of the barrier role of the border' (Popescu, 2012: 70), often through efforts aimed at reducing or eliminating barriers between European border regions, fostering integration and cooperation.

Rather, debordering emerges as a proactive response to challenges and opportunities that transcend national boundaries. Newspaper narratives covered many examples of cooperation and Interreg projects, as well as cross-border infrastructure projects designed to diminish the boundary function of the border in question. For example, an article about the Slovak-Hungarian 'Castle to Castle' Interreg project to renovate four castles and forts in the border region noted that 'these settlements are all peripheral border locations, suffering of emigration and a lack of local jobs'. Accordingly, the project to establish a common, cross-border tourist route offers them the opportunity to be attractive for several-day visits (*Új Szó*, 4 February 2020).

Our media analysis reveals that debordering initiatives often gain traction in contexts where economic, social, or cultural interdependencies underscore the benefits of openness, connectivity and network- or infrastructure-building. As already mentioned, during the Covid-19 crisis, media coverage highlighted the plight of cross-border workers navigating differing regulations and the subsequent calls for streamlined processes to facilitate their mobility. Economic stability and tourism also feature prominently in debordering discussions, as seen in efforts to reopen borders for cross-border shopping or to develop transnational tourist routes such as greenways and cycle paths. Moreover, in regions such as the Franco-German border region, debordering initiatives seek to (re-)connect local communities, language minorities, and shared cultural identities, emphasising inclusivity and mutual benefit. These examples illustrate how debordering strategies promote regional resilience and collaboration, challenging traditional notions of borders as barriers and instead framing them as opportunities for cross-border cooperation and mutual prosperity.

Functional integration

We discovered quite a few narratives that present an increasing degree of functional integration of cross-border labour markets, infrastructure and tourism and consumption in a positive light. A network logic is presented as allowing for a better everyday life: this can be seen regarding both very technical implementations (drinking water pipelines) as well as more straightforward network creations (transnational bike lanes).

For example, in the French-German border region, be it in times of crisis or in normal times, the weakening of the geographical border, but also to some extent of mental and legal borders, is presented as a positive event for tourism, consumption and the continuity of landscapes. The tourism aspect is also often highlighted, as it appears that one of the key successes of cross-border cooperation as practised in the Eurodistricts and Euroregions is the development of cross-border greenways and cycle paths. Private cooperation on both sides of the border is also moving in the direction of 'debordering' to encourage tourism:

The coronavirus will have put off opportunities to get to know each other: never mind, as soon as the restrictions are lifted, meetings between the managers of French and German spas will resume. The aim is to attract spa-goers from neighbouring countries (*DNA*, 21 March 2020).

This example is significant in illustrating the vision shared on both sides of the border on the desirability of 'debordering.' This is because those who could be presented as competitors, who would have an interest in border closures, prefer instead to agree in seeking to specialise so as to maximise their appeal in the eyes of the French (who are in the business of health care with thermal water) and in the eyes of the Germans (who consider thermal baths as wellness). Similarly, France and Germany created a new form of tax cooperation because living and working on either side of the border can cause many bureaucratic problems, such as those of cross border pensions (*DNA*, 25 May 2020).

Tourism development also played an important role in the Slovak-Hungarian border region, where there was likewise cooperation between different spas in the wider borderland (*Új Szó*, 16 April 2021). There were also reports about numerous EU-supported projects ongoing in the borderland, e.g. on a laboratory for wine in Mužla (*Új Szó*, 10 October 2019) or on boosting the borderland's tourism industry (*Új Szó*, 4 February 2020) that was portrayed as an opportunity to become more attractive for several-day visits. In an effort to strengthen tourism, there have been developments of common infrastructure such as web sites and the creation of Europe's largest cross-border bike rental system (*Új Szó*, 19 May 2021). Furthermore, there were reports (*Új Szó*, 2 July 2021) of new and old infrastructure projects involving the construction of bridges.

In both Polish newspapers under consideration, *Gazeta Wyborcza* and *Gazeta Lubuska*, 'neighbourly Europe' is presented as a form of labour market integration: here, local and regional stories are reported in which borderlanders are presented as beneficiaries of labour opportunities in Germany, as activists for opening the border during the pandemic restrictions ('We scream, open the border!', *Gazeta Wyborcza*, 24 April 2020) or as citizens who participated in the raising of new bridges to Germany (*Gazeta Wyborcza*, 14 October 2021). On the German side, too, one can see a narrative of competition-turned-into-cooperation:

We started off very euphorically and felt superior. After 20 years, this has been put into perspective: countries like Poland and Czechia are hungry for success and prosperity and have also caught up in terms of know-how. Today, Polish entrepreneurs say it has never been so easy for them to deliver to Germany. They have caught up technically, they are more market-oriented and their pricing structure is cheaper. ... We just have to look for new cooperation partners further afield, in Hof and Munich, in Kassel and Hamburg, in Walbrzych and Boleslawice. (*Sächsische Zeitung*, 30 April 2024).

Or, as a Polish economic actor quoted in *Sächsische Zeitung* put it:

For years, the companies only saw each other as competition. ... I hope that we can coordinate structural change across borders. A German-Polish coal commission would actually make sense, where experts work together with

politicians to develop sensible projects across borders. (*Sächsische Zeitung*, 30 April 2024).

Also related to functional integration is a planned bridge over the Neisse/Nysa/Nisa river on at the Polish-German-Czech border. The territory of the Euroregion Nisa is crossed by the rivers Nisa (between Germany and Czechia in the three-border point) and Oldřichovský potok (between Poland and Czechia in the three-border point), where the borders of Czechia, Poland and Germany meet. Discussions on the construction of a common footbridge uniting the three countries were initiated in 2004, when Poland and Czechia joined the EU. However, the construction itself has not yet commenced, due to difficulties with permits, funding and ground conditions (*Idnes.cz*, 27 July 2020). 'European ideas on the ground' under the conditions of everyday technicalities prevent the construction. One can detect a good deal of frustration locally about the delay, which in turn speaks to a strong desire among locals to have better connecting infrastructure.

Such a desire is also clear among the narratives in the regional media from Germany's border region with Poland and Czechia, where there is a critique about lacking agreements on cross-border emergency services. Lacking rail connections are also part of this narrative, as seen in the coverage of a trilateral memorandum between local and regional politicians from Zittau, Liberec, Hrádek and Bogatynia, to demand improved cross-border rail infrastructure (*Sächsische Zeitung*, 4 November 2019; *Idnes.cz*, 4 November 2019) or of a tour of the so-called 'Rübezahl-Express', a promotional train journey of Polish, Czech, German and French Social Democratic candidates for the European Parliament to demand that 'the EU should grow together at the member state borders' (*Sächsische Zeitung*, 29 April 2019). In all these narratives, a lack of connecting infrastructure is juxtaposed with what local politicians, journalists and borderlanders think they should have, namely the infrastructure to cross the border and use services on the other side more easily. Thus, it is a narrative that sees borders as all too visible and seeks to make them more invisible.

Reconnection to a local transborder reality

There are also narratives that seek a return to the achievements of the past. This is particularly important for language minorities, disrupted cooperation networks and families, which were already discussed above. In essence, this narrative implies a 'return to normal' after the pandemic.

For example, in the Slovak-Hungarian border region, one article title (*Felvidék.ma*, 1 September 2020) 'Now we again don't belong together for a while' in response to Hungary's border closure, implies that people from both sides of the border used to belong together. In a similar vein, an opinion piece stressed that it was thanks to the Schengen Area that crossing borders had become part of many people's everyday lives in the Slovak-Hungarian border region, and especially among Hungarians on both sides (*Felvidék.ma*, 11 September 2020), and where there used to be 'a very lively and active traffic' across the border (*Új Szó*, 15 May 2020). On the aforementioned infrastructure projects across the Slovak-Hungarian border, 'both countries are making efforts to halt the unnatural conditions along the border by which friends, relatives, acquaintances and neighbours are torn apart' (*Új Szó*, 2 July 2021).

A similar sense of reconnection was seen in the Franco-German border region, where debordering initiatives seek to reconnect local communities and reactivate shared cultural identities. This was captured in headlines such as 'Binational couples will be able to reunite' (*DNA*, 17 September 2020) or statements from Franco-German spa managers such as the following: 'as soon as the restrictions are lifted, meetings between the managers of French and German spas will resume.' (*DNA*, 21 March 2020).

6. Relations with Europe and the European Union

Understanding relationships between neighbouring countries often differs from getting a regional understanding of the perceptions towards the European Union. While neighbouring country relations are shaped by immediate, bilateral interactions, the EU represents a broader, more complex political and economic endeavour. In this sense, animosity or friendship towards another European country certainly does not map easily onto an overall stance on the EU as a whole. This distinction is crucial, as it highlights the different lenses through which people view their neighbours versus the EU. What is more, the terms 'Europe' and 'European Union' are not synonymous, and this ambiguity frequently complicates the discourse around European integration. In our analysis, we focus on the European Union and highlight whenever a connection is made between the more general 'Europe' on the one hand and the EU on the other.

The media analysis reveals distinct narratives that shape perceptions of the EU and its role in the region. These narratives can be broadly categorised as 1) Euroscepticism, 2) Eurodistance, 3) Europhilia, and 4) a sense of disillusionment that links with Eurorealism and efforts at reform.

1. **Euroscepticism:** this reflects a critical stance towards the EU, often questioning its effectiveness, legitimacy, or influence. This narrative can be seen in regions where there is significant distrust or dissatisfaction with EU policies. For instance, the media in the Polish-German-Czech border region often highlights conflicts and rivalries, such as the Turów coal mine dispute, which can exacerbate negative perceptions of the EU, as the dispute touches on European law. Euroscepticism can also manifest itself in criticisms of the EU's handling of crises, such as the Covid-19 pandemic or immigration issues, where national interests are perceived to be at odds with EU rules.
2. **Eurodistance:** this describes a more neutral or ambivalent attitude towards the EU. It is characterised by a pragmatic approach to EU membership and policies. Benefits and drawbacks are weighed carefully. This narrative is prevalent in regions where local interests occasionally clash with EU policies, but where there is no outright rejection of the EU. For example, in the Danish-Swedish border region, local narratives often focus on the practical implications of EU policies on daily life, balancing national sovereignty with the advantages of EU membership.
3. **Europhilia:** represents a positive and sometimes enthusiastic endorsement of the EU. This narrative is driven by the belief in the EU's potential to promote peace, stability, and prosperity. It is particularly visible in regions with strong cross-border ties and a history of cooperation, such as the Franco-German border region. Here, media narratives frequently emphasise the benefits of European integration, including economic growth, cultural exchange, and enhanced mobility. Initiatives such as the Erasmus programme and cross-border infrastructure projects are celebrated as symbols of European unity.
4. **Disillusionment and Eurorealism:** disillusionment arises whenever the EU fails to meet the high expectations implied by some of its ideals, leading to frustration and disenchantment among citizens. Such disillusionment often fuels 'Eurorealism'. This is a pragmatic approach that seeks to address the EU's shortcomings by advocating for reforms that emphasise national sovereignty, democratic principles, and practical benefits for member states. Eurorealism calls for a realistic assessment of the EU's strengths and weaknesses and pushes for changes that align with the diverse values and identities of European nations, thereby addressing the root causes of disillusionment.

6.1 Euroscepticism: A borderland accentuation

The concept of Euroscepticism in border regions is often accentuated by the unique challenges and frustrations that people in these areas face. The intricate nature of EU bureaucracy, regulatory constraints, and cross-border disagreements significantly contribute to a heightened sense of scepticism towards the EU. This section explores how these factors manifest themselves in specific border regions, drawing on examples from Poland, Germany and Czechia to illustrate the broader implications of EU policies and their reception.

Bureaucracy, clashes of interest, and elitism

One narrative in border regions is frustration with EU bureaucracy, particularly concerning the complex and restrictive nature of funding rules. This idea has been highlighted particularly clearly in the Polish-German-Czech border region. Here, one can detect an overall narrative of good intentions colliding with bureaucracy, some of it at the European level. For example, the abovementioned planned footbridge across the Nisa river to connect the three countries has been in the planning for twenty years, but as of 2024, construction had not begun, also due to the impossibility to fund trilateral projects from bilateral Interreg programmes there (*Idnes.cz*, 14 November 2022). This is partially due to difficulties with permits and ground conditions but also related to EU funding rules (*Sächsische Zeitung*, 9 May 2022). This narrative can also be traced in other local incidents, such as the successful police cooperation project 'Limes' facing significant funding issues due to delays in the approval of the EU budget (*Lausitzer Rundschau*, 19 November 2019). These examples convey a broader narrative of inflexibility of EU bureaucratic rules, compounded by inertia at the national and regional levels of governance. Together, these problems can impede effective cross-border collaboration and timely responses to local problems.

More generally, there can be a perceived clash between local sectoral interests and the strategic direction of the EU in some areas. This can be seen in a series of articles about Polish farmers' protests against EU agricultural policy. They carried out these protests by blocking Polish-German border crossings (*Sächsische Zeitung*, 2 May 2024). There is a complex relationship here both with the EU's environmental policies, as well as the import of Ukrainian agricultural goods, which posed strong competition to Polish farmers. While the Polish Tusk government is strongly pro-Ukrainian, it tried to listen to the grievances put forward by the farmers, hold a dialogue with Ukrainian authorities, and seek an EU solution to the problem (*Gazeta Wyborcza*, 23 February 2024). A similar article appeared in *Wyborcza* on 2-3 March. This time the author of the text urged the Polish government to treat the concerns of protesting farmers seriously. How populists intend to utilize the farmers' dissatisfaction with the EU's Green New Deal and the import of goods from Ukraine was judged as worrisome.

Gazeta Lubuska, which became more Eurosceptic after being taken over by Orlen in 2021, does not specifically focus on bureaucracy but rather offers a generally values-based narrative of Euroscepticism: criticisms here are centred on allegations of EU undemocratic practices, imposition of costly policies, and excessive centralisation of power. The newspaper has amplified voices critical of the EU from various countries, portraying dissatisfaction as widespread, even within traditionally pro-European states like Germany. This narrative advocates for a democratic and sovereign Europe, opposing what is presented as elitist EU tendencies and advocating for a Europe rooted in national sovereignty and Christian values. From this perspective, a call is made to the 'real Europe' which incarnates the opposite to the western values like the acceptance of LGBT+ rights. However, following the change in the editorial board in 2024, the fiercely populist, Eurosceptical, or Eurorealist positions – with unconcealed criticism of Germany as the main driver of the EU, and attacks on liberal and leftist parties as allied with Brussels and Berlin against Law and Justice – were in retreat.

Cross-Border conflicts and national narratives

The analysis of newspapers from the Polish-Czech-German border region also offer insights into how specific cross-border conflicts can exacerbate Eurosceptic sentiments. This is especially visible in two examples which occurred within our time-period under consideration:

The Turów coal mine dispute: the expansion of the Turów coal mine is the most prominent issue, causing significant tension between Czechia and Poland on the one hand and some communities in Saxony and Poland on the other. Many of the articles selected focus on the environmental impact, legal battles at the European Court of Justice (ECJ), and the bilateral agreement reached between Poland and Czechia in 2022. The Czech and German local populations' opposition to mining and the role of local governments in negotiations are also highlighted in the narrative. Some German borderlanders and local and regional politicians are presented in the narrative as feeling powerless and being frustrated by the EU's perceived lack of help: '[Zittau] feels left out in the cold. Why does the EU not help?' (*Sächsische Zeitung*, 2 May 2024). Similar feelings were identified in Czechia, too: '[The Polish-Czech intergovernmental agreement] only provides a legal cover for further mining in Poland, which clearly breaks the European law and rights of the local people' (*idnes.cz*, 25 October 2022). The Czech complaint to the European Court of Justice (ECJ) over ecological damage caused by the Polish coal mine in Turów near the border intensified Eurosceptic and anti-German – but not anti-Czech – narratives on the Polish side. This is because *Gazeta Lubuska*, at this point with a firmly anti-German and Eurosceptic editorial line, equated Germany with the EU and framed attacks on the EU as a defence of Polish sovereignty. The ECJ's decision to impose a ban on coal extraction in Turów and subsequent fines for non-compliance provided a platform for *Gazeta Lubuska* to criticise the energy policy of the EU, which was presented as pro-German. The dispute was framed in Poland as a bilateral issue between member states, with EU involvement portrayed as harmful and unnecessary. This narrative supported the Polish government's efforts to negotiate directly with the Czech authorities, bypassing the EU.

The Odra river pollution: controversies over the causes of water pollution in the border Odra river between Poland and Germany was presented on the German side as an example of deceitfulness on Poland's part, as the mysterious pollution appeared to originate on the Polish side, but no explanation was given. While this was presented as a bilateral and regional problem in the German media, on the Polish side, it further intensified Euroscepticism. Media outlets like *Gazeta Lubuska* used these conflicts to criticise the EU, often equating it with German dominance. The newspaper's rejection of the EU's right to impose fines on Poland for non-compliance with EU law was portrayed as a defence of Polish sovereignty against perceived German and the EU overreach.

However, as noted above, *Gazeta Lubuska* abandoned its narrative of equating Berlin with Brussels and the implied link between negative attitudes towards Germany and Euroscepticism after the editorial team changed in 2024.

6.2 Eurodistance: A sense of periphery

The concept of Eurodistance encapsulates the sense of detachment and peripheral relevance that certain regions feel towards the European Union. Unlike Euroscepticism, which actively critiques the EU, Eurodistance is characterised by a more passive disengagement, where the EU is perceived as distant and its decisions as less impactful on daily life. This section shows how this sentiment manifests itself in various regions, especially in the borderland contexts of the Slovak-Hungarian border region and the Öresund region.

In the Slovak-Hungarian border region, there is a notable absence of EU-related troubles and a lack of blame directed towards Brussels. This region does not exhibit the same intensity of frustration with,

or criticism of the EU as witnessed in the Polish-German-Czech border region. This relative tranquillity suggests a pragmatic acceptance of EU policies without significant conflict, but it also reflects a certain disengagement from EU-related issues, indicating a Eurodistant perspective.

Another aspect of Eurodistance is the perceived difficulty in engaging with EU authorities. It has been shown that people in Lusatia, for instance, find it challenging to connect with EU decision-makers in Brussels, both physically and in terms of understanding the bureaucratic processes. This perceived distance reinforces feelings of neglect and marginalisation, contributing to a sense of Eurodistance where EU affairs are seen as remote and disconnected from local concerns. This stance was also found to a certain extent in the Franco-German case. While the Franco-German relationship is prominently covered in both French and German regional press as being positive and based on ‘friendship’, German newspapers adopt a more technical and sometimes Eurodistant or even Eurosceptic tone when discussing the EU as an institutional reality. This tone underscores a critical perception towards EU regulations, portraying them as overreaching or insufficiently addressed. This is the case, for example, when *Die Oberbadische* headlines ‘The EU is heading for a slippery slope’, denouncing the draft European directive proposing tests every five years to check that holders of driving licences are still fit to drive and to combat road accidents. We read: ‘Once again, they are exposing themselves to the suspicion of wanting to regulate down to the smallest detail the lives of some 450 million people living in the countries of the Union. But it’s not just in faraway Brussels that ageing motorists are in the crosshairs’ (*Die Oberbadische*, 14 November 2023).

The analysis of the Öresund region reveals a broader pattern of Eurodistance:

- **Depoliticised media coverage:** finding media pieces related to the EU in the Öresund region is challenging, reflecting a Eurodistant attitude where EU decisions are not seen as central to daily life. This pattern persists even during significant events like the 2019 European elections and the COVID-19 pandemic. This finding is consistent with previous literature (Svensson 2020; Svensson and Nilson 2023). When the EU does feature in the media, it is mainly seen as a rule giver, with technical regulations reported in a depoliticised manner. For example, the European Commission’s ban on cod fishing in the eastern Baltic Sea was reported factually without much political context, illustrating again a prominent Eurodistant narrative.
- **Nordic cooperation overshadowing EU integration:** there is a sense of distance from the EU as regions emphasise closer Nordic cooperation. The idea that Scandinavia or the Nordic Council stand out as unique and more real than the distant EU further underscores the Eurodistant narrative. Discussions about a potential Nordic state confederation reflect a desire to prioritise regional values and cooperation over broader EU integration. A quote from an interview published in *Bornholms Tidende* illustrates this idea: ‘I think that a closer Nordic cooperation, preferably a Nordic state confederation, where the Nordics undertake to stand together internationally but also in relation to our welfare society and the important values we have in the Nordics, is good. Globally, the Nordic welfare society is unique, and we have to look at how to defend the Nordic values in a globalised world’ (*Bornholms Tidende*, 3 June 2022).

The same narrative can be seen in the coverage of the 2024 European elections, which led to more coverage of the EU than in non-election years. Most of the reporting tended to cover the national picture and focus on major election issues such as climate and security. One particular politician mentioned in the run-up to the election was Morten Messerschmidt, the leader of the Danish People’s Party. In the articles he, as expected for a Eurosceptic leader, cited concerns with immigration in general, as well as criticising the EU for the damage he perceived it to have done in many areas. It is still not possible to detect a clear Eurosceptic narrative, but articles covering less EU-positive parties contained some references, like when writing about the Danish People’s Party or about the Swedish Sweden Democrats.

We have lost in many parts of the country. I think it is difficult to get our voters to vote in the EU elections as there is skepticism about the whole system, says Michael Rosenberg, SD's strongman in Helsingborg. (*Helsingborgs Dagblad*, 10 June 2024).

Coverage of the elections also included featuring politicians with local (but not cross-border) anchorage:

She will be the only Malmö resident in the European Parliament: Jonas Sjöstedt is accompanied to Brussels by a lawyer from Malmö. The Western Party's electoral success gives Hanna Gedin a seat in parliament. - To have someone in place in Brussels, I think Malmö deserves that as the country's third largest city, she says. (*Sydsvenskan*, 10 June 2024)

In this way a geographical representation mindset was introduced to the European Union elections which is otherwise lacking in the one-country-one-list approach of the two countries, but this mindset does not stretch to borderland representation. One article featured a borderland panel, though: one election debate took place on the ferry running between Danish Helsingør and Swedish Helsingborg. An issue of borderland relevance covered during the debate was the maritime space and the possibility to create a national maritime park.

In summary, a Eurodistant narrative in various regions manifests itself as a sense of detachment from EU affairs, with EU decisions perceived as less central to daily life. This sentiment is shaped by discrepancies in EU support, challenges in engaging with EU authorities, and media narratives that emphasise regional over EU concerns. Even during the European elections, when the EU featured more prominently, the narratives were predominantly Eurodistant rather than clearly Eurosceptic.

6.3 Europhilia

'Europhilia' manifests itself distinctly in border regions, reflecting a blend of idealism, pragmatism, and symbolic values associated with European integration. In *Gazeta Wyborcza*, a Polish narrative of European integration is framed through both idealistic and pragmatic lenses. Idealistic articles critique reducing the EU to a mere economic benefactor (EU is not 'ATM cash machine', *Gazeta Wyborcza*, 23 May 2019), advocating instead for adherence to EU laws and standards as a reflection of Poland's commitment to a visionary European project ('Athenian democracy, Roman law, Christian decalogue, Renaissance humanism, Enlightened rationalism – all this makes European tradition. Also the Polish one', *Gazeta Wyborcza*, 18 May 2019). Simultaneously, *Gazeta Wyborcza* underscores the concrete benefits of EU membership, celebrating developmental and civilisational advancements facilitated by EU integration. The EU is portrayed as indispensable in addressing global crises, emphasising its role in enhancing Poland's prosperity and security, particularly in borderlands like Lubuskie voivodeship where EU investments are credited with stimulating economic growth ('Who betrays the EU, betrays Poland as well', *Gazeta Wyborcza*, 1 May 2019).

In the French-German borderland, especially in Saarland and Lorraine, the idea of Europe as a solution against some the radical solutions of 'far away Berlin' or 'far away Paris' has also been witnessed. In this sense, there is a narrative of the European Union being closer to the citizens than the capitals insofar as Europe helps people facing crisis locally (such as that of Covid-19) better than the distant national government in Paris or Berlin. Such was the case with a German citizen living in France and stating: 'People from Berlin know nothing about our cross-border region. We're the ones who live here, it's not up to them to decide for our region' (*Le Républicain Lorrain*, 5 March 2021).

On the French side of the French-German border, Europhilia occasionally transitions into great enthusiasm for European integration, characterised by symbolic and values-driven narratives. French media coverage during Covid-19-related border closures often took on moral and ethical tones, exemplified by the ‘Umbrella Movement’ protests against border restrictions (*Dernières Nouvelles d’Alsace*, 27 December 2020). This narrative emphasises Franco-German friendship and the foundational spirit of the EU, focusing more on symbolic unity than detailed institutional analysis. Exceptions to this symbolic focus include discussions on post-Covid-19 European economic initiatives, albeit with limited exploration of local impacts. Overall, for border residents, Europe is presented primarily as an identity experience, encapsulating both symbolic European ideals and everyday concerns. This is exemplified in Jean-Christophe Meyer’s reflections on this dichotomy when he commented on the criticisms of a local who complained about consumerism taking precedence over all other considerations when the borders were first opened after the Covid-19 crisis: ‘Sometimes we’re a long way from symbols, from Europe...’ (*Dernières Nouvelles d’Alsace*, 16 June 2020). The fact that so many local companies or public entities, in Alsace especially, decided to call themselves ‘European’ probably also bears some significance. To give but a few examples out of hundreds: ‘Le centre européen du résistant déporté’ [European resistance and deportation Centre], the ‘école européenne de chimie et des polymères’ [European School for Chemistry], the ‘Centre Européen d’Actions Artistiques Contemporaines’ [European Centre for contemporary artistic actions], etc. Even the city of Strasbourg has added the European term ‘Eurométropole de Strasbourg’ [Eurometropolis Strasbourg].

One can also detect elements of Europhilia in Poland, specifically in the more pro-European newspaper, *Gazeta Wyborcza*. Unlike *Gazeta Lubuska*, his newspaper does not present the EU as a foreign, external, transcendent, or intrusive being. In this narrative, Poland is presented as firmly rooted in Europe. Even the *Gazeta Lubuska* at the height of its ‘Euro sceptic phase’ at one point presented Poland as the EU’s last bulwark against a threat from the East. This was specifically the case on the occasion of the migrant crisis that was reported on in Poland in the second half of 2021. The mission to protect the European external border was presented as a manifestation of ‘Europeaness in us.’ Here, the narrative of (auto)immunological borders is echoed, albeit not in a Covid-19 context but rather in a context that presents the body politic as needing protection from external threats. We may label such unexpected Europhilia in an otherwise overwhelmingly Euro sceptic and Euro realist newspaper (as the paper was between 2021 and 2014) as cynical or selective: European ties are celebrated as authentic and beneficial in those rare occasions when Poland needs more EU, but in ordinary circumstances they are rejected as ideological and harmful.

Following the Polish election of 2023 and the resultant change in government, elements of Europhilia became more evident. *Gazeta Lubuska* reported on European and Polish figures welcoming the change of government, even quoting the European Commission President von der Leyen as welcoming Poland back to European values (like some wayward child). This change in government was also swiftly followed by the abolition of EU sanctions against Poland, with a narrative that stressed that Poland would get ‘the pile of the EU money’ (24 February 2024, *Gazeta Lubuska*).

On the 20th anniversary of Poland and Czechia joining the EU, one can detect a narrative of the EU as a benefactor, especially in the Polish and German media. Several articles put forward a very positive assessment of the benefits EU enlargement, and the two countries’ accession to the Schengen area has brought (e.g. *Sächsische Zeitung*, 30 March 2024). For example, one Polish photographer resident in Görlitz noted the disappearance of bureaucratic hurdles and the need to queue when Poland joined the EU and the Schengen area (*Sächsische Zeitung*, 27 April 2024). In contrast to Poland and Saxony, there were no similar narratives in researched Czech media outlets.

6.4 The narrative of disillusionment and Eurorealism

Various other narratives shape perceptions of Europe beyond the three main groups that our analysis so far put forward: Europhilia, Euroscepticism, and Eurodistance. This diversity reflects the complex dynamics and the evolution of attitudes towards European integration. In addition, one can detect some narratives of disillusionment when the EU fails to meet high expectations.

As already outlined above, there were some narratives in the Slovak-Hungarian regional media accusing 'Brussels' of being 'asleep' in the early stages of the pandemic (*Új Szó*, 5 May 2020). The SME narrative criticises the EU's crisis management fund as insufficient, inferring a decline in trust in the EU. While this could be construed as a Eurosceptic narrative, it actually hinges on the perception that the EU *should* be doing more. In such a context the perceived lack of action brings disappointment and disillusionment. However, ultimately it still comes from a place of trust, albeit misplaced trust, in the EU according to the narrative.

On the German side of the Polish-German-Czech border for instance, this idea of disillusionment is exemplified in local reactions to pandemic-related border closures and bureaucratic challenges for workers. These instances reveal a stark contrast between the ideal of free movement within Europe and the practical realities faced by individuals and communities. This theme was also visible on both sides of the Franco-German border, showcasing the idea that European integration should be much stronger: 'how can we still have borders closed in 2021!' (*DNA*, 27 December 2020). Such a sense of disillusionment is then followed by more realistic and less idealistic perceptions of the European Union.

At the Polish-German-Czech border, one can also detect narratives that could be described as envious of the smooth cooperation perceived across Western European borders. For example, regions like the Meuse-Rhine Euroregion are presented as benefitting from smoother cross-border coordination. However, such a narrative does not necessarily lead to disillusionment; it can also be a motive to aspire to better structures. In this narrative, solutions to local problems by emulating the structures in Western European border regions are offered. Furthermore, Western European initiatives are presented as a model for Central European border regions. For example, one article describes an initiative in the second chamber of the German parliament of the three German regions bordering Poland (Saxony, Brandenburg and Mecklenburg-Vorpommern) to expand Polish-German relations. Several Franco-German initiatives such as a bi-country Interrail ticket or a citizens' fund are taken as a model that should be emulated in the Polish-German border region. Also, the article noted that the Polish government would increase its funding to the Polish-German Youth Organisation, which again is modelled on the Franco-German equivalent. In other words, the envy narrative ultimately is one of the border as a connection, and the aspiration is for a level of bilateral cooperation equal to that between France and Germany (*Lausitzer Rundschau*, 2 May 2024).

Similarly, in Polish media narratives published around the 20th anniversary of Poland in the EU, some Europhilic articles contained some Eurorealist criticism about EU rules not fitting Polish specificities. For example, the opposition of the new Polish government towards the EU's Migration Pact was discussed on 15 May 2024 (*Gazeta Lubuska*, 15 May 2024). The journal cited the statement of the government that the new rules do not acknowledge the specificity of Polish borders/external borders of the EU, especially the border tensions provoked by Belarus.

These diverse narratives underscore the multifaceted nature of Europe's relationship with its borders and the EU, reflecting ongoing debates and interpretations that shape public opinion, policy discourse, and regional dynamics across the continent.

7. Conclusion

Our media analysis in four very different border regions has illustrated the way in which meaningful events such as the Covid-19 pandemic, which affected all border regions, or the controversy over the Turów coal mine, which was localised, are woven into broader narratives, as produced by journalists, politicians at all levels but mostly not borderlanders themselves. These narratives, in turn, are not always related to the European Union and the European integration process. However, insofar that they do relate, we have seen that seemingly contradictory narratives can exist side by side. For example, we have detected some mildly Eurosceptic media narratives on the German side of the usually very pro-European Franco-German border region. Likewise, we have encountered Eurosceptic as well as Europhilic narratives in the Polish-German-Czech border region and even within the same newspaper, namely *Gazeta Lubuska*.

Nevertheless, on the whole, it is safe to say that the media narratives in the Franco-German border region were predominantly Europhilic in the period under consideration. They were predominantly Eurodistant in the Danish-Swedish and Slovak-Hungarian border regions. In the Polish-German-Czech border region, we have found the strongest current of Euroscepticism, notably in the narratives from *Gazeta Lubuska*, though also in some German media narratives. However, as mentioned before, Eurosceptic narratives in this region are complemented by Europhilic and Eurorealist ones.

Some of the master narratives identified in Opiłowska et al. (2023) were clearly reflected in the media narratives from our four border regions. The narrative of crisis in Europe was clearly present in the coverage of the Covid-19 pandemic. It is important to be clear that this crisis was presented less of a crisis 'of Europe', i.e. a crisis of Europe's own making, but rather a crisis that occurred in Europe (as elsewhere in the world).

The narrative is entwined with one of the (in)visibility of borders. Again, the bordering measures, such as border closures and subsequent introduction of filtering functions for borders, clearly collided with a long-perceived narrative of borders being invisible to most borderlanders. The disruption, which was covered through narratives of the suffering of commuters and families, provoked strong reactions of locals, most – though not all – of whom opposed these measures. Thus, we can frame this as a narrative demanding a return to the invisibility of borders.

However, in this the narrative of the (in)visibility of borders clashes with two others, namely a narrative of the (in)securitisation of borders and a narrative of auto(immunological) bordering. For example, in the context of crime and migration, the media narratives, and those of local and regional politicians, are frequently supportive of bordering measures. In both these narratives, borders with a strong bounding function are presented as increasing the security of both the borderlanders and the country at large. At the same time, as noted at the outset, a securitisation narrative continues to draw attention to a threat and may thus be unlikely to increase the perceived security of Europeans.

Narratives of borders as (auto)immunological tools could be detected in a Covid-19 context, even though resistance to the sweeping border closures was strong. At the same time, such narratives can also be detected in response to other threats presented as external threats to the bounded European space. This narrative was most visible in the Polish media narratives about the Polish border with Belarus, which coincides with the external EU border. The sense of using the external border to protect the European space from threatening immigrants and asylum seekers was also echoed in the German media narratives from the Polish-Czech-German border region. Here support for bordering contrasts with the aforementioned resistance to it in a Covid-19 context. It appears that bordering initiatives are questioned more when they affect all, but less so when they affect those 'others' that have come to embody the perceived external threat, i.e. migrants and asylum-seekers as well as criminal people smugglers.

Given the ethical values connected with the right to asylum, we anticipated a narrative of (in)humanitarian borders. Such a narrative would draw attention to how securitised borders may clash with humanitarian values, in turn generating calls for humanitarian action. However, this theme was largely absent from the newspaper coverage we analysed. This may have been a result of our search criteria, which focused mostly on our four intra-EU border regions, whereas asylum claims still tend to be concentrated at the EU's external borders. However, some of the narratives of a securitisation of the external EU borders were framed as having local relevance, e.g. on the German side of the Polish-German-Czech border region. Given that such a connection is made for the threat but not the critique of inhumanitarian borders would seem to indicate that there is an important blind spot in local media narratives.

In a similar vein, we did not encounter any self-critical narrative demanding a reinvigoration of the universalist promise of the European idea. The closest narrative to this is the debordering narrative of a reconnection to a local transborder reality. Still, with the best will of the world, spa managers reconnecting across the Slovak-Hungarian or Franco-German borders is hardly comparable to a narrative of Europe as an embodiment of debordering, cosmopolitanism, and triumph over of parochial boundaries.

One final observation is that one can detect some links between local border narratives and broader perceptions of the European Union. However, these links were not as prominent as we anticipated. In a majority of the narratives, there was little connection between local narratives and Eurosceptic or Europhilic narratives. Some of these arose from a sense of Eurodistance. In other cases, local crises or local manifestations of broader crises were regarded through a local lens only. Thus, while borders are a 'forgotten factor' in analysing perceptions of the EU (a fact that motivated our B-SHAPES project), it appears that links with the EU are also a forgotten factor in border regional narratives.

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Our study is foremost a media analysis, most of the displayed citations are therefore quoted from the local newspapers that were selected for each region (see *infra* section 2.1). This reference section will thus differentiate between those newspapers' quotes (**A**) and the academic literature that has been used to understand and comfort the analysis of the newspaper materials (**B**).

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